

PLEIADES

Technical brochure induction welding

PLEIADES – Advancing Aerospace Composites Through Induction Welding and New VitrimERIC Formulations Enhanced by Integrated Photonic Sensors, Providing Data to Digital Supply Chain, SHM, Maintenance.

www.pleiades-project.eu

PLEIADES has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101192721.

Funded by
the European Union

Why Weldable Composites Matter

The aviation sector faces growing pressure to reduce its environmental footprint, with CO₂ emissions expected to double by 2050 unless major innovations are deployed. Every 100 kg of weight saved in an aircraft can translate into fuel savings of up to 600,000 litres over its lifetime. Advanced composites already play a critical role in reducing weight and improving performance, but to unlock their full potential, the industry must adopt faster, cleaner, and more sustainable joining methods.

Unlike conventional mechanical fastening or adhesive bonding, welding composites enables lighter, stronger, and more repairable aerostructures. Thermoplastic composites and next-generation vitrimeric resins bring the added benefit of recyclability and reshaping, making them ideal candidates for sustainable manufacturing. However, to fully realise their potential, robust welding processes and real-time weld quality assurance are essential.

Our Approach in PLEIADES

PLEIADES combines automated induction welding with integrated photonic sensors to deliver a breakthrough in weldable aerostructures. By embedding passive, EMI-free photonic multi-sensors directly

into weld zones, we achieve real-time monitoring of temperature, pressure, and refractive index, enabling adaptive closed-loop control of the welding process.

This ensures:

Consistent, high-quality welds across both thermoplastic and vitrimer joints	Shorter cycle times and reduced energy consumption (up to 25%)	Reversible disassembly and re-welding, extending component life and reducing waste	Embedded data for structural health monitoring and digital twins

Why it matters

Weight & Efficiency

Expanding weldable composite applications reduces weight and improves aircraft fuel efficiency, payload, and range.

Sustainability

Thermoplastics and vitrimers are recyclable, repairable, and aligned with circular economy principles.

Safety & Reliability

Real-time weld quality monitoring ensures repeatability and reduces defect risks.

Digital Transformation

Embedded sensing integrates with SHM and digital supply chains, enabling predictive maintenance and reduced lifecycle costs.

Impact targets

30-40% cost savings in manufacturing and maintenance

25% reduction in cycle time and energy use

Improved damage detection speed

Reduction in defect-identification training effort

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101147532.